

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BRUCE****FIRST NAME: JULIAN****PROGRAM CODE: DRTM****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

The author applied US of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 05%

The author used the following software: Windows 11, Google Docs

1. Euclid LMS Course Video (EUCLID 2001)
2. What is a Style Guide (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 41)
3. Plagiarism Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 14)
4. When NOT to Cite (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 37) and (Common Knowledge 2021)
5. Tables (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 53-54)
6. Argue Against Yourself (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 14)

AN INTRODUCTION TO EUCLID UNIVERSITY'S COURSE STRUCTURE AND CITATION GUIDELINES

1) INTRODUCTION

In this response paper, I will summarize key elements discussed in the *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack*, a document intended to outline in great detail the many aspects of writing a post-graduate academic essay. I have highlighted five topics that I found exciting and discussion-worthy instead of mundane and obvious. I approached the discussion on these ideas from the lens of a new Ph.D. candidate in Translational and Research Medicine. I expanded the scope to include insights a scientific researcher would consider applicable and valuable. Considering my background as an MBBS student and that my future short-form and long-form writings will mostly be scientific, I decided to go the extra step and analyze the coursepack from the viewpoint of not just an academic but as a future physician-scientist.

The six topics of discussion for this response paper include a summary of the Euclid course summary video as well as explanations of the fundamental component of a style guide, causes of plagiarism, when it is appropriate not to cite information, the usefulness of tables, and the importance of arguing against oneself in academic writing. I supplement

the readings by interjecting my own thoughts on the content and chiming in with my opinions on things that I learned, as well as times I may agree or disagree with the material.

2) **EUCLID LMS COURSE VIDEO**

After watching the Euclid LMS course video, I learned the standardized structure of every course Euclid offers. Each course comprises seven self-paced study periods that align with standard in-person campus practice. Of those 7 study periods, 5 require the submission of a response paper similar to this one. Each response paper uses a globally compliant template which every course will utilize. Period 6 requires the candidate to take a 10-question quiz and create their quiz. Each course concludes with a period 7, 40-minute capstone oral examination over Zoom.

The Element LMS system, which EUCLID students use to log in and view their course syllabus, was modeled after the system utilized by Coursera. Once enrolled in a course, students can access reference textbooks for in-depth study. When a course is completed, the LMS system will generate a LinkedIn or Credly certificate of completion to display as a sign of professional development. I use LinkedIn regularly and look forward to highlighting these certificates on my page. This will boost my academic and professional profile in the short and long term (Euclid University 2015).

3) **WHAT IS A STYLE GUIDE**

The *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack* describes a style guide as “a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent...[and] provides a means of documenting basic rules or features of your writing...” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 41). Reading the coursepack was my first exposure to the concept of a style guide. Although it may seem straightforward, it considers many aspects of a person’s writing, ranging from big ideas such as depth of treatment matter and readership considerations to more nitpicky things such as symbols or abbreviations. The latter is things I seldom think about in my writing that I now realize are areas of concern. Even the trademark or branding consideration aspect is seemingly outside the scope of stylistic choices I rarely have to consider. However, moving forward, I will try to consider these things when appropriate.

As a previous freelance writer, it is essential that freelancers “demonstrate an ability to follow a prescribed style, but equally that you can learn and record what your customers prefer from their comments” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 42). When I wrote USMLE-style questions under the guidance of previous NBME authors who were not serving as my direct editor, learning the style in which they wanted me to write was vitally important. Much of the editing process was centered around stylistic changes to my writing style so that I best matched the writing style of the actual test writers. At first, I thought I had it all figured out, but after many conversations with my editors, I began viewing my writing from the lens of both a student test-taker and a highly trained test writer. Being able to

review my editor's comments and quickly interpret the changes they recommended made me a better technical writer and, in the end, a better test taker myself.

4) **PLAGIARISM**

By the time a candidate reaches the post-graduate level, given their length of education up to that point, a general understanding of what constitutes plagiarism is expected upon enrollment. As students who have progressed through more than a decade of teaching and likely completed at least 4-6 years of graduate-level academic work, the idea that one should not plagiarize is not contentious. We all know intentional plagiarism is unacceptable and can be grounds for failing a paper, course, or degree.

The more realistic concern related to plagiarism is non-purposeful plagiarism resulting from an improper citation of information and quotes taken directly from an outside source that is not novel to the author. Most at this level generally understand how to cite information correctly, but the fine details must be clarified and often outright ignored. A lot of this stems from ignorance of the rules or conflicting information students find online. The *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack* states,

“Plagiarism comes in two forms, both unacceptable. First, you plagiarize when you use the words of a source without quotation marks. If you take words from a source, you must use quotation marks, not just a footnote. Moreover, you should not present a close paraphrase from a source: either use the exact words with quotation marks or restate the point in your own words” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 14).

This type of plagiarism is more prominent and less likely to be an honest mistake. It has been clearly defined since writing, even very young, that using another person's words and trying to mask them as your own is blatant plagiarism. When inserting another author's content word-for-word into your paper and attempting to hide the fact by leaving out essential quotations is behavior that calls into question not just the intention but also the ethics of the said individual. To maintain the trust of our professors and future colleagues, we, as researchers and authors of academic papers, must always write and share information ethically and honestly. We should never put ourselves in a position where our integrity is questioned in this way. The best way to avoid that is carefully review our work to ensure all necessary quotations are in place and err on the side of caution and give credit to an author if you have a clue that an idea originated with them and is not uniquely your own.

The second type of plagiarism is one I need to become more familiar with the second type of plagiarism because it requires a style of writing I do not use myself. How this type of plagiarism occurs is described as follows, “Second, you plagiarize if you take ideas from a source without footnoting the source. Sanctions for plagiarism depend on its severity and may range from lower grades on an assignment to a failing grade for the course” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 14). After further research online, Purdue Online Writing Lab explains footnotes as “...supplementary details printed at the bottom of the

page pertaining to a paper's content or copyright information" (Footnotes & Appendices 2022). It explains that footnotes are more appropriate over formal quotations when the content is short and focused rather than lengthier sections which are better situated in the body paragraphs. I now understand that footnotes are appropriate for snippets of information that can get the point across despite their short length. Although I do not have experience with this formatting type, I will attempt to experiment with it in my future writings to see if it can improve my writing more directly.

5) **WHEN NOT TO CITE**

A topic from the *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack* I do not believe had ever been specifically explained to me was the "When NOT to Cite" section. The preceding discussion on instances when it is acceptable to use information from a source and not cite it was an essential matter not part of my previous education. I was unaware of the following:

"When the information you are writing about is common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas, you do not need to cite its source...The basic rule you can use is that if it is repeated in many different sources, then you can assume it is common knowledge" (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 37).

The concept of common knowledge not needing to be cited has entered my consciousness as an author. After examining why this is important in preparation for writing this response paper, I now understand that this rule exists to lessen the need to cite sources in an academic paper excessively. Although the bulk of the content contained within the research should be new and thought-provoking, there will be background information that is generally known and understood that can be discussed straightforwardly and without reference to any single source. This is meant to ease the writing process and allow writers to discuss topics that would otherwise be left out if required to track down the source of information, which is now long forgotten and sometimes impossible to do.

Considering I am pursuing a Ph.D. in Translation and Research Medicine, in the future, I will fall back on the advice given by the "*Yale Poorvu Center for Teaching and Learning*" when they write,

"The sciences, however, have a somewhat different notion of "common knowledge," coming partly out of research practice and partly out of more collaborative work methods. Ideas, findings, and methodologies that are new knowledge (and therefore specialized rather than common) become old knowledge more quickly in the sciences. The answer, again, is to consider the messages you're getting from the course about what concepts are common or foundational, and to check in with professors or TFs" (Yale 2021).

This is particularly relevant advice to me, a Ph.D. candidate in the biological sciences who may need help to effectively weigh information and data as new and specialized vs. old and general. I will come across new and sometimes controversial information that I must

analyze compared to old, generally accepted data. Knowing when I must cite something instead of when I am allowed to mention something without further responsibility is a valuable skill that will keep me academically honest and out of suspicion of even non-purposeful plagiarism. However, when unsure if something requires a citation, a good rule of thumb is “When in doubt, cite it.”

6) **TABLES**

The text goes on to discuss the appropriate reporting of levels of probability, explicitly stating, “Tradition dictates the use of asterisks to annotate statistics in the table, for example: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$ ” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 54). I am happy to see mention of the presentation of statistical information as it pertains to tables. I am good at understanding and applying these values, and I hope to use them when appropriate in my future research. As it stands now, I understand what p-values represent, but I do not yet know how to calculate them myself. I am confident there will be a future lesson on calculating these values but knowing how to list them in a table that matches international standards and formatting is an excellent first step.

I agree with the statement, “A table offers an excellent means of presenting a large number of individuals, similar facts so that they are easy to scan and compare. A simple table can give information requiring several paragraphs to present textually, and it can do so more clearly” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 53). Tables are a great way to convey sometimes vast amounts of numbers or pieces of information of similar type in an easy-to-digest format. For a person like myself that is good with numbers and math, tables like this have great significance in presenting data to a reader.

I disagree that “An informative table supplements-it does not duplicate the text” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 54). There will be instances when a table that summarizes the text in an organized and easily palatable manner should be used in academic writing. Sometimes information is conveyed across multiple paragraphs or deals with vast amounts of data, which may appear convoluted if presented in large blocks of text. Instead, giving this information in a table where all the data can be analyzed in a single place may be more appropriate. I try to avoid absolutes as I tend to believe that it is acceptable for people to differ in how they present information as long as they do so without intending to deceive, confuse or misrepresent data. Some people may prefer to restate their written text via the use of a table so that they can capture the attention and understanding of a wider audience, and I do not see the harm in that.

7) **ARGUE AGAINST YOURSELF**

A good rule of thumb about how to effectively best attribute the views of an external source with minimal fear of misrepresenting them is to “argue against yourself” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 14). Taking a conflicting pros and cons approach to presenting an argument is good standard practice as it maintains the appearance that the

author is honest and forthcoming. It also allows the reader to make an informed decision on their own, especially when a topic may be controversial and currently being debated publicly.

Because we students rarely have direct access to an author of a text we want to reference, we inevitably will have to make informed judgment calls about the author's intent and meaning. We should not assume the author makes a claim or formulates an argument without analyzing their biases. An author would look silly by stating something as a matter of fact without presenting counterarguments or listing even minimal information. It would seem quite apparent that almost nothing in the world today can be stated with absolute, 100% certainty. Instead, we should assume the author has taken the time to consider alternative viewpoints and weigh them against their own. Therefore, presenting their views as all-positive or all-negative would be unfair. Instead, we should aim to deliver all sides of an argument or the most popularly debated sides (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 14).

Attempting to maintain a fair balance between what we choose to highlight as truth and what we highlight as false without listing them as “fact vs. fiction explicitly” means we are taking steps to manage our biases. This allows the reader to judge based on the information presented. We will try to persuade the reader one way or another, while we may want to leave any conclusions open-ended at other times. Either way, we should strive to provide relevant data, whether in support or in contrast to our own beliefs, and not purposefully withhold critical information. We seek the truth; sometimes, pursuing truth means debunking our inherent notions.

8) **CONCLUSION**

In conclusion, after watching the Euclid introductory video and analyzing the elements of a style guide, common causes of plagiarism, when citations are unnecessary, contents of tables, and why arguing against oneself in academic writing is necessary, these sources have taught me many important lessons on how to write a post-graduate research paper properly.

Writing is a strong suit of mine, but the fine details often need to be noticed. I am generally a content-focused individual, and this coursepack opened my eyes to many areas of writing I have yet to consider or understand the importance of. As I continue to write more and more response papers, I will get the opportunity to utilize much of the knowledge gleaned from this exercise. As a result, the value will become more apparent over time. As this is the first time many of the fine details are being presented to me, my understanding still needs to be improved and far from flawless. However, I will strive to put into practice the information I learned through this first part of the course, as I know that taking the time to cite references in real time and presenting data in an easily understood format will save me time and effort down the line.

REFERENCES

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